

MESS 0028

GEO 2.24: Proposed Comparison of Electrogeological Scales via height/elevation and diameter comparison, along with proposed origin vectors

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ABSTRACT

The field of Electrogeology is very new, perhaps less than 30 years old. Its best work, however, has come within the last 10 years, and certainly for this author the last 1 year. A number of trip reports and MESSies have created a major impact that backs up the tables found in previous EPEMC work. In this paper we example heights, depths, and widths along with proposed EG mechanisms, and speculate somewhat openly about the sources. Direct comparisons are made, and a few conclusions regarding expectations are drawn. However, the cross-section of data (20 sites) is still too few, given the variables, to draw any firm conclusions about source vectors, mechanisms, and sizes.

Keywords: electricity - geology - Grand Canyon - Kentucky - lichtenberg

Introduction

MESSies 0018-0023 provide some of the best electrogeometrological (EGM) evidence yet provided anywhere. But, it raised the same questions as the author had raised in 2019 on “The Electric View,” if these structures are formed via electricity, as the evidence seems to suggest, would not there have to be different sources, depending on the sizes, diameters, elevations, etc... in order to create them. Through studying them, systematically, we may be able to discern the number of vectors, and perhaps the sources themselves. So far the only guaranteed external sources are the Moon (as EDM) and Jupiter, via induction. These two sources are however not likely the only sources. It isn’t clear that Jupiter would have provided any EDM via arc, although it may have created uplift at various times. But though we see direct connections between Io and Jupiter, and we see electro volcanology, we do not see direct arc EDM. So we must seek out all the sources possible, which appear to include: The Moon, Jupiter, Saturn, Mars, Venus, [Metis], Neptune, Mercury, and perhaps the Galilean bodies.

Comparison Tables

The following table is not meant to be exhaustive, merely useful for this study.

Table 1 - EGM Cross Comparison

<i>Structure Name¹</i>	<i>Height or Elevation ↑ ground</i>	<i>Diameter/ Width</i>	<i>Anode (A) or Cathode (C)</i>	<i>Proposed Vector</i>	<i>Proposed Source</i>
Big Sink (c)	-20' to -30'	5900'	A	Inducted pulse	Jupiter
Pine Mountain²	1745'	1.5 miles	A	EDM	Moon
Upheaval Dome (c)	750'	3000'	C	Arc	Shamash
Shiprock³ (m)	1583'	1640'	A	Arc	Mars
Knobs Region	850'	14 miles	A	Lichtenberg	Jupiter
Hick's Dome⁴ (c)	666' or 4000'	10 miles	A	EDM	Comet?
DBNF leyline⁴	1125'	10 miles	C	EDM	Shamash
Stone Mountain (m)	750'	490'	A	Arc or EDM	Venus
Ayers Rock/Uluru (m)	1142'	1.8 miles	A	Arc	Moon or Venus
Pilot Knob, NC (m)	1400'	2 miles	A	Arc	Jupiter
Pilot Knob, KY (m)	1440'	2904'	A	Arc	Venus
Indianfort, KY	1503'	2 miles	C	Arc	Venus
The Black Hills	5500'	335 miles	C	EDM	Shamash
Half Dome (m)	1360' or 4737'	1 mile	A	Arc	Jupiter
Grand Canyon	-5000' (avg)	18 miles	C	EDM lichtenberg	Venus or Moon
Devil's Tower (m)	867'	800'	A	Arc	Shamash
LBL & Fluorite District	-75' @ ~ 500'	~10 miles	C	EDM→E field?	Jupiter
Hudson Bay Crts (c)	-111' to -300'	250 miles	C	Arc pulse	Comet?
Carolina Bays⁵ (c)	-50'	~300'	C	Sputtering Arc	Moon
Richat⁶ (c)	330'	25 miles	A	Birkeland Arc	Venus
Wudang Mtn.	5289'	~6.3 miles	C	Arc	Shamash

¹ In descending quality of evidence; (m) = monadnock; (c) = crater

² [MESS0020: GEO 2.21 - Andy Hall's Crooked Smile Hypothesis Proven by the Pine Mountain flux](#)

³ [Trip Report: Shiprock and Barringer Crater](#)

⁴ [Trip Report: Pebble Beach, Red River Gorge](#)

⁵ [Plasma Petroglyphs \(Plasmaglyphs\), Earthworks, and the Megafauna Extinction p59-60; and Part 1](#)

⁶ [Ashes of Atlantis Part 1](#)

Analysis: Proposed Vectors and Evidence - a living reference

Looking at the EG scales⁷, and sorting by height, and then separately by width, it seems that definitely width is more of the direction that we want to go. It seems that cathode behavior tends to be at the wider behaviors, although it is proposed that the Bays are cathode structures. One must bear in mind that there are four types of lightning, where you can move the anode and cathode, and you can go ground to source or source to ground. Therefore, our primary interests are in the spreadsheet's near repetition of behaviors. Monadnocks tend to be smaller, and craters larger. Mountains and chains are obviously the largest, while lichtenberg's formations are massive, too.

Structures in the millions of feet tend to be cathodes, and their sources are mysterious. Potentially Shamash, or a comet (electro-bolide), or Venus, Jupiter, or Moon. It isn't clear how much electric field involvement, if any at all, is majorly involved (but it is hard to picture none at all.).

When sorted by height, we see a lot of similar height to similar source issues. And it is proposed that it is the self-similarity of the type of electric current that is being thrown out. It is to be thought that diameter, therefore, is primarily related to anode vs. cathode, but also of source size (potential voltage), while height is related **directly** to the proposed source, based on ages (all speculative) and Vector type. The lower heights, and depths, tend to be specially named vectors, while the higher locations tend to be Arc, EDM, or both. Electric Discharge Machining is mysterious in electrogeology, so the simple continuous pulse arc is much easier to understand. But some of these arcs were moving, and etching, either raising or lowering the bodies on the **very thin** crust. The best example, clearly, is the Pine Mountain Flux, as it demonstrates the Hall-Yelverton Crooked Smile Keystone (CSK).

Meanwhile, there are other excellent A++ and A+ evidenced sites, which are very different, in almost every way (every column), and this does present a lot of challenge for the public and the mainstream of geology to see the repetition of form. A light/easy example is the Grand Canyon vs. Knobs lichtenberg. The GC is much deeper than the Knobs are tall. One is clearly anode and the other cathode, but why the etch, and the source size (pool of charge) is not clear either. Also while we see the Knobs has a specific burn region, the Grand Canyon was excavated and we can only look into it with our intuition (at this stage of technology, until we use automated drones with electromagnetometers of high precision to LiDAR map it in B & E fields). See the two structures below for direct comparison. We can see the subtle differences of these formations from standard fluvial behaviors, which are electric but wracked with surface tension and kinetic physics, which aren't present in pure electrical flow.

When we look at the proposed vectors and sources, we see a lot of speculation based on size of the source, as well as expected aging of the structure. However, outside of the Perattian Thunderbolt at Big Sink⁸, actually we can only rely on [faulty] mainstream dating, and this is totally problematic. It means that we have to go back to myths, as in the case of Shiprock, which is definitely not 27 million years old, and has a mythic origin story dating from the time after the breakup of Shamash. It is a legendary time between 9ky and 13kya, and it is unknown how long of that time it would have taken to form, although it is presumably short. As short as minutes/hours to days based on lab evidence. With electro-bolides/comets it could be even less.

There are problems for the electro-bolide, but evidence is needed to prove that EDM can produce the same bow shocks we see at Middlesboro Crater and at Hicks Dome. Such formations don't appear to happen at many other sites. There are small lips at the Carolina Bays, but this issue needs a rotating surface to test, under lab conditions.

⁷ [+ Electrogeology Scales](#)

⁸ [= Discovery of Perattian Thunderbolt of the Gods Strike Location](#)

Table 2 - Comparing Lichtenberg

Figure 1 - The Grand Canyon; credit: Google
Average Depth: 5000'
Average Width: 95,040'

Figure 2 - The Knobs Region; credit: Google
Average height: 850'
Width: 73,920'

Let's - for fun - overlay them on top of one another in transparency, and note some features from Hall-Yelverton theory

Figure 3 - Overlay of the Lichtenberg formations that have Grade A and A++ evidence; credit: author

*Note that they have similar scales, although the Grand Canyon etching is very dominant in vein width as compared to the knobs uplift regions; and this reflects the scale of height, probably indicating charge. It would be expected, though, that their total scales are similar because the body that produced them made contact for a similar amount of time and/or angle of instance. Figure 3 will be examined again in the future.

Looking at these features, it could be Earth→Earth self-arc EDM in a bygone era of high electrification!

This is a very exciting development of this paper, which was unexpected, and precisely the reason we do this kind of EGM work, as well as theoretical and fieldwork. It's important to make side-by-side and direct overlay comparisons, looking for correlations. For example the wide portion of the main canyon is 15.2 miles wide and the Knos is 13.9 miles wide from north to south. Nothing here is conclusive, but it is interesting.

Some other interesting coincidences... the Pilot Knob, KY and Indian fort (as well as Zion Mountain) occurring at the junction where the Grand Canyon has a major escarpment to the right where the little Colorado River has fallen in.

It is important to note that fluvial erosion *is happening* in the Grand Canyon... mostly because the Colorado River has fallen into the excavation. You can see the difference of its V-shaped carving and the upper vertical region where etching *may have* occurred (meaning the EDM is not as deep as reported), in this photo:

Figure 4 - the Grand Canyon; credit: author (May 2022)

Conclusion

The facts of the state of EGM study is that it is still in its infancy, and many test conditions need verification. Also, fieldwork, theoretical physics and cymatics/shockwaves, etc. have to be combined with the framework of EGM to find ways of explaining **all phenomena**, not merely some of it. This is the primary failing of mainstream tectonics-only [uniformitarian] geology. It is a capital mistake⁹ that we do not plan to repeat in EPEMC!

⁹ MIMS 2.10.1-.3 - MESS0025: Investigation - Sir Arthur's Gift

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